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Thierry of Flanders .

Thierry of Flanders, 1159 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1166
February 16 B .

Thierry of Flanders, 1157 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1139 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1149 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1146 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1142 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1147 .

Thierry of Flanders, 1166
February 16 A .

Henry the Lion
1172 No. 2 .

Henry the Lion
1172 No. 1 .

Ansculf of Senots .

Enguerran II de Coucy 1138 .

Enguerran II de Coucy 1168 .

Phillip of Flanders
1176 .

Phillip of Flanders
1177 · Charters .

Rudolf of Pfullendorf 1180 .

Fulk of Anjou & Companions .

Rainald · Charters .

R. Gabard .

Berlay II of Montreuil, 1120 .

Fulk of Anjou, 1129 .

Berlay III of Montreuil-Bellay, 1162 .

William the Huntsman

Hugh of Amboise ·

Guy Tortus of Rochefort ·

Baldwin of Vern d'Anjou ·

Geoffrey Fulcard of Loudun ·

Fulk of Plassis-Macé

henry-the-liberal

Peter of Curcellis 1178 · Charters ·

Henry the Liberal, 1181 between March 10 and 16

Henry the Liberal, 1179 · Charters ·

Henry the Liberal, 1179-1180 (6) ·

Henry the Liberal, 1179-1180 (2) ·

Henry the Liberal, 1179-1180 (3) ·

Henry the Liberal, 1179-1180 (4) ·

Henry the Liberal, 1179-1180 (5) ·

Henry the Liberal, 1179-1180 (1)

walter-of-hereford

Walter of Hereford, 1165-1178 ·

Archiving Dossier